

(De)constructing the professional identities of third space practitioners through zine making

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DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845014>

This activity provided participants with a medium for constructing, and deconstructing, their professional identity through zine making. Participants were encouraged to reflect on their professional identity within the third space through a proposed lens of academic counterculture – a space where identities intersect, and experiences and titles blur beyond recognition. The diverse communities traditionally represented in zines provided a valuable construct for reflection on professional identity in the third space. The activity leveraged zines as a medium to promote community-building and connection – a platform to construct meaning and to connect those working, or existing, in often lonely spaces.

Provocation

Participants worked through a short, interactive microlesson to explore zines through counterculture movements, the zine-making process, and provocations for utilising zine-making to construct and reflect on professional identity in the third space. Padlets were included in the microlesson to share artefacts and reflections, with examples curated from colleagues who have previously worked through the materials. The activity was designed to be both low and high touch, depending on the level of engagement. Participants could complete it in one to two hours. The session was built upon previously tested methodologies and pedagogies from a book chapter and workshop (Molloy & Thomson, 2023, 2024).

Reflection

As a third space practitioner and emerging researcher, testing this activity in a “safe space” like the 3SS was a unique opportunity. While I regularly leverage creative methods in practice, I hope to use zine-making workshops to collect data as a creative method further along in my PhD research. It was useful to avail of this space and community to test the process early on and carefully consider how participants might perceive my third space as academic counterculture provocation. Upon reflection, the activity should be less structured and include ample opportunity for participants to identify their own themes or lenses with which to construct professional identity. A significant takeaway was that all participants chose to create a digital zine as opposed to scanning a handmade artefact when provided with both options, and it will be worthwhile to pursue the “why” in future sessions.

References

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